

Suggestions for Low Cost Multifunction Sensing

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ABSTRACT

Modern aerospace vehicles must perform a large number of sensing functions, but to fit within modernization budgets they must do it at very low cost. A modular, multifunction, open architecture, sensing system required of EO systems on a combat aircraft will be discussed. Multiple aperture modules will be used, and one or more systems modules will encompass common components. Target acquisition will be analyzed for a large forward looking aperture, while missile warning, situational awareness, IRCM, and other functions will be considered through multiple situational awareness apertures. A low cost multifunction RF system that is divided into three areas defined by analog to digital, A/D, converter state of the art will be discussed.

INTRODUCTION

First we will discuss the development of a modular, multifunction, open architecture, system capable of accomplishing all of the functions required of EO systems on a combat aircraft. This system will be very

Communications is mostly a low band system (< 2 Ghz). Electronic warfare has a unique problem requiring a wideband receiver. Radar needs very high dynamic range but can use narrow band A/Ds.

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affordable fashion through maximum use of common components as well as commercial off the shelf (COTS) components, when available. Later in the paper we will discuss a multifunction radio frequency, RF, system. Figure 1 shows an aircraft-based view of the Multifunction Identify, Strike, and Survive Integrated Optical Nodules, MISSIONS, concept, the multifunction

EO sensor system. Wherever possible common components will be placed in an environmentally benign region of the aircraft, and shared among the various apertures. Desired functions will be re-examined to see if they can be accomplished in affordable ways that maximize use of common components and identical components while striving for reasonable systems simplicity. Complete azimuth coverage is envisioned as well as adequate elevation coverage (possibly on the order of -45 degrees to +15 degrees, although full elevation coverage is desirable). Multiple aperture modules will be used, and one or more systems module will encompass common components. A single systems module could be sufficient, but for battle damage resistance, and possibly for space availability reasons, it may be necessary to have more than one systems module. In a concept demonstration, a single systems module is sufficient.

When implementing the MISSIONs concept it is important to design it as a portion of a modular, multifunction, open aperture, avionics suite. This will allow maximum use of any synergy or affordability

opportunities between EO systems and other avionics functions, such as the multifunction RF system to be discussed later. Certainly some processing functions can be shared, as well as a high-speed digital data bus. Some analog functions can probably be shared. The MISSIONs system should include all functions that can affordably be accomplished with EO / IR systems. Candidate functions are: 1.) Air to ground target acquisition and identification at ranges in excess of 20 Km (for tank size mobile targets such as a Russian T -72); 2.) Target designation against air to ground targets, even if the MISSIONs equipped aircraft turns for home after the target is acquired and the weapon is released; 3.) Hand-off to Global Positioning System , GPS, based munitions, or combination GPS / seeker based munitions; 4.) Air to air target acquisition and identification at ranges in excess of 60 Km (for the infrared signature of an F-16 size target without any plume); 5.) Very high probability of infrared missile countermeasure against all A/A and A/G threats, to include modern threats that have anti-flare discrimination circuitry and imaging seekers;

Figure 1. Aircraft-Based View of a MISSIONs System

6.) Missile approach warning as support for the infrared countermeasures function; 7.) Countermeasures against 8 -10.5 μm thermal imaging sensors that may be adjunct trackers for threat systems; 8.) Navigation update by locating fixed objects on the ground using pilot situational awareness sensors (This day / night imaging capability may be used for a landing aid in adverse weather or black out conditions and for functions such as air to air refueling); 9.) Covert inter-aircraft communications using solar blind / atmospheric absorbed UV laser communications; High bandwidth laser communications to satellites or other aircraft at high

altitude; 10.) Laser Doppler wind measurement for targeting, bomb drop, airdrop, and safety / economy of flight purposes. Figure 2 shows a conceptual diagram of a MISSIONs system which incorporates the complete set of candidate functions. MISSIONs system cost and the mission of a particular aircraft will be factors in deciding which of the above functions should be available in a given aircraft implementation. Each aircraft type may need a somewhat different implementation of MISSIONs. It is anticipated that a MISSIONs demonstration will encompass most of the above functions.

Figure 2. Conceptual Diagram of a MISSIONs System

As a preliminary example of the design trades, which must be evaluated, consider a seven aperture MISSIONs system. The number of holes in the aircraft can be substantially fewer if no FOV restrictions are present, since multiple telescopes could be mounted in the same aircraft hole. Conversely if obscurations are present we may need more than seven apertures and more than seven holes in the airplane. Nominal coverage could be 60 x 60 degree coverage for each of 6 situational awareness / countermeasure / designator / laser communications apertures (referred to here as situational awareness apertures), and a smaller FOV forward coverage for one large target acquisition / ID aperture. Once a target is acquired in the front aperture it will be necessary to establish active track, and to be capable of handing over that track from the acquisition aperture to the situational awareness apertures. The target designator will be kept on the weapon delivery spot in an over the shoulder delivery by handing off tracking and designation from the acquisition aperture to one or more situational awareness apertures. It is possible that multiple situational awareness apertures will be used for laser designation as the aircraft turns. The baseline approach considered is for each of the six situational awareness apertures to have a 2.5 cm diameter, while the forward target acquisition aperture would have a 10 to 15 cm diameter.

One design restriction on the aperture modules is that the product of aperture diameter in centimeters and instantaneous FOV of that aperture in degrees is restricted, based upon the F# of the system and the largest dimension of the focal plane array (FPA). For an F 1

system, and a maximum dimension of 2.5 cm (1 inch) on the focal plane, the product of aperture diameter times instantaneous FOV is 150 deg*cm. For a 5 cm focal plane (2 inches) on a side this product is increased to 300 deg*cm. For example if we assume a 5 cm on a side FPA, then we could have a 10 cm forward-looking aperture with a 30 degree FOV. Since this is a large focal plane, we will assume a 2.5 cm FPA for the six situational awareness apertures (to keep costs down). Then we can have six 2.5 cm diameter apertures around the plane that have a 60 degree instantaneous FOV. If full 4π coverage is desired then each aperture would have to cover a 90 degree FOV, so either the FPA would be larger or the aperture would have to be smaller. It is likely that cost and space constraints will limit the size of these aperture. To cover the angular area required the acquisition aperture would have to step stare due to these constraints. Table 1 shows some of the acquisition aperture possibilities.

Table 1. Acquisition Aperture FOV and Diameter Options

<i>FPA side dimension</i>	<i>Aperture diameter</i>	<i>FOV</i>
5 cm (2 inches)	10 cm	30 degrees
"	15 cm	20 degrees
2.5 cm (1 inch)	10 cm	15 degrees
"	15 cm	10 degrees

AIR TO GROUND TARGET ACQUISITION WITH AN EO SENSOR

The air-to-ground target acquisition sensor must provide a long-range (20-km) detection capability against clear and camouflaged targets in clutter. The required detection range and the conflicting requirements of excellent detection performance and area search capability dictate the inclusion of techniques such as Hyperspectral / multispectral passive sensing and microscanning which can improve detection performance with a relaxed detector angular subtense (DAS) requirement.

Consider the cases of 1.5 and 3 meter cross range ground resolution at a 20-km detection range, and a 6-km sensor platform altitude. This is about a 19-km detection ground range. This corresponds to angular resolutions of 75 and 150 μ rad. Using the Rayleigh resolution criterion¹, the diffraction-limited angular resolution for a circular aperture is given by:

$$\theta = \frac{1.22\lambda}{D} \quad (1)$$

where

λ = wavelength

D = diameter of the aperture

This corresponds to the peak-to-null halfwidth of the Airy disk, and is approximately equal to the full width between the half power points². Using equation 1, diffraction limited resolution at a 9 μ m wavelength is 110 μ rad for a 10 cm aperture, and 73 μ rad for a 15 cm aperture diameter. Therefore, a 10-cm aperture would support the 3-m resolution case, but a 15-cm aperture would be required for the 1.5 meter case.

Microscanning can be used to provide diffraction-limited resolution with a larger DAS. For target detection in clutter using multispectral techniques it is optimistic at this point to assume acceptable detection performance with pixel sizes greater than 3 meters. In the 1.5 m resolution case using a 15 cm aperture, therefore, we can consider two variants: (1) 150 μ rad detector angular subtense (DAS) using microscanning for resolution enhancement, and (2) 75 μ rad DAS without microscanning. In the first case a 10-cm aperture could be used.

Considering the 150 μ rad DAS case, a 640 x 480 FPA has a FOV of 5.5 x 4.1 degrees and a 1024 x 768 array has a FOV of 8.8 x 6.6 degrees. The swath width searched in these two cases is shown as a function of range in Table 2.

Table 2. Searched Swath Width (150 μ rad DAS)

Range (Km)	Pixel cross range size (meters)	640 az elements (Km)	1024 az elements (Km)
20	3	1.92	3.07
15	2.25	1.44	2.3
10	1.5	0.96	1.54
7.5	1.13	0.72	1.16
5	0.75	0.48	0.77

For cued targets the search swaths given above are easily sufficient. For uncued targets we need to assess whether we should provide a wider search swath, especially when weather limitations determine that sensor detection range is consistent with the shorter ranges listed in table 2. For an aircraft flying at 300 meters per second, Table 3 gives area searched per minute.

Table 3: Searched Area per Minute

Range (Km)	640 az elements (Km ²)	1024 az elements (Km ²)
20	35	55
15	26	41
10	17	28
7.5	13	21
5	9	14

A detection cross range resolution of 1.5 - 3 meters was assumed at 20 Km in the above analysis. For classic Johnson criteria this would mean we could only detect targets with a minimum dimension larger than 3-6 meters.³ For a cluttered situation detection / false alarm probabilities would not be acceptable even for these large targets because the Johnson criteria does not apply in heavy clutter. In heavy clutter even larger targets would be required for detection. Hyperspectral / multispectral sensing has a good chance of obtaining necessary detection and false alarm probabilities with samples this large even against heavy clutter. In low clutter situation even larger target spatial sampling could be used to search with acceptable probability of detection and probability of false alarm. Microscanning allows the preservation of spatial detail even with a larger DAS for supporting spectral and combined spatial-spectral detection methods.

A zoom telescope can be used to provide a pilot the choice of search resolution. With a zoom telescope the area searched would not necessarily be reduced as a function of target acquisition range because the FOV can be increased to maintain the same ground sample size with range. Maximum search area given in table 2 could

then be maintained if the pilot decided. Conversely, the pilot could choose to achieve better spatial resolution at the shorter ranges with reduced FOV. To allow equal spatial sampling from 7.5 km to 20 km ranges implies a 2.6 : 1 zoom capability. To optimize detector performance throughout the zoom, the optics should be designed to maintain a constant $f/\#$ throughout the zoom range. This implies that the effective aperture diameter will decrease at the shorter ranges.

Table 4 below gives the required look down depression angle for a target acquisition sensor as a function of altitude and detection range. This table assumes a zero pitch aircraft attitude, so any up angle in aircraft attitude would require an additional depression angle.

Table 4 Required Depression Angles

Altitude	Ground Range	Depression Angle
6 Km	20 Km	16.7 deg
6 Km	15 Km	21.8 deg
6 Km	10 Km	30.9 deg
6 Km	7.5 Km	38.7 deg
6 Km	5 Km	50.2 deg
5 Km	10 Km	26.6 deg
5 Km	7.5 Km	33.7 deg
5 Km	8 Km	32 deg
300 meters	7.5 Km	2.3 deg
300 meters	5 Km	3.4 deg
300 meters	2.5 Km	6.8 deg

We can see from Table 4 that we need depression angles, which range from 2.3 degrees for a long-range acquisition at low altitude. We need between a 30 and 50 degree depression angle for short-range acquisition from high altitude. If we restrict ourselves to a 30-degree Field of Regard (FOR) in elevation, and cover long range acquisition from low altitude (2.3-degree depression), then we would have about an 8-Km minimum acquisition range from mid altitude (32-degree depression). This assumes that in marginal weather the pilot is willing to acquire targets from a 5-Km altitude rather than a 6-Km altitude. An 8-Km minimum acquisition range based on elevation angle sets the

minimum weather in which the system is useful. Regardless, ability will be required to steer the FOV of the target acquisition sensor in elevation.

To broaden the search capabilities, as well as to allow functionality with a variety of attack tactics, the acquisition sensor should also provide a large azimuth FOR. Ideally, this would be at least 60 degrees. One method to expand the FOR is to use two counter-rotating prisms. This is not a high tech solution, but for moderate timescale slewing it is a simple and reliable approach. It would allow us to slew the FOV in any direction. Large angle slewing requires wedges made out of high index material since a large optical path difference is required to tilt the phase front over a large angle. If no resets are used and the system remains broadband, then Table 5 gives the maximum path delay required for a 10 cm aperture and the wedge thickness required depending on the index of refraction of material used.

Table 5 Path Delay and Wedge Thickness
(assuming a 10 cm aperture diameter)

Angle	Path Delay	Wedge	Wedge
		Thickness (index = 3)	thickness (index = 1.7)
30 degrees	5.7 cm	2.9 cm	8.2 cm
15 degrees	2.7 cm	1.3 cm	3.8
10 degrees	1.8	.9 cm	2.5
5 degrees	.87	.4 cm	1.25

MULTISPECTRAL AIR TO GROUND CONCEPT DESIGN

This section offers a conceptual design of a passive multispectral sensor intended to satisfy the requirements described above for long-range air-to-ground targeting, including capabilities against CC&D and deep hide targets.⁴ The description will be broken down in terms of the generic FLIR components outlined in Figure 3: optical imaging system, spectral separation/filtering device, focal plane array(s), readout/control electronics, calibration sources, stabilization and pointing system, and on-board digital processing.

Figure 3. Generic Components of a FLIR System

It is important that the optical imaging system be very well achromatized to insure excellent band-to-band spectral correlation. The ideal configuration is a completely reflective optical system. Clearly there are a range of designs which could be satisfactory, including the Cassegrain telescope arrangement shown. Firm requirements for spatial resolution have not yet been determined. For the purpose of this paper, however, consider the case of 1.5 - 3 meter resolution at a 20-km nominal range. This can be satisfied with a 15-cm diameter, $f/2$ optical system and 20-micron detector pitch. As shown earlier a 15-cm aperture has sufficient resolution to obtain about a 1.5 meter cross range pixel size at 20 Km.

Various arrangements can be considered for spectral separation and filtering. The need for very tight band-to-band spatial registration, however, favors implementations that allow excellent optical registration of bands. One such arrangement uses dichroic filter elements to separate the input energy into three spectral channels. This configuration is radiometrically efficient, but requires the use of three FPAs, is not very compact, and is likely to be sensitive to vibration-induced band-to-band misregistration. Another approach is the use of on-chip spectral filtering. The primary limitation of this basic approach is in achieving spectral simultaneity and band-to-band spatial registration. Some proprietary designs exist for resolving this limitation. Probably the optimal configuration is the use of true multispectral focal planes if and when FPA technology matures to the point of making it practical (e.g., multispectral MQW GaAs).

Considering the optimal three-band design (8.7, 9.15, and 9.35 micron band centers; 200 nm bandwidth), the FPA choice is essentially limited to MCT in the near

term with the potential for MQW GaAs in the future (unless one is willing to provide a 20 degree cooler necessary for extrinsic Silicon focal planes). 640 x 480 element MCT arrays with 20-micron pitch are currently being developed. Therefore, it is not unrealistic to consider a future 1024 x 768-element device. With a 1.5 meter pixel cross range at 20 Km (75 μ rad angular resolution) this would provide a FLIR FOV of 4.4 degrees azimuth by 3.3 degrees elevation, or greater than 1 km frame width on the ground. For current CCD well sizes, even with the limited spectral bandwidth, the FPA must be operated at a high frame rate (low dwell time) to avoid saturation.

Beyond the standard timing, control, and readout electronics needed for any FPA, this design will require a 12 bit digitizer and a high-speed 16 bit frame coadder to achieve the necessary Signal to Noise Ratio, SNR. Considering the 500 Hz frame rate and 1024x768-frame size, the pixel data rate is nearly 400 MHz. This necessitates about 32 parallel digitizer channels to accommodate the rate.

In either spectral separation configuration, the multiple spectral bands are sensed with different detectors. To achieve excellent band-to-band correlation, it is essential that the detector-to-detector responsivity and offset variations and fluctuations be properly corrected. At least two-point calibration using blackbody references at each of the two temperatures is required to perform this task.

Significant cost savings may result if fine stabilization could be performed electronically. With the array reading out at 500 Hz, fairly modest pointing means

will provide adequate stabilization within the frame time. Therefore, if frame-to-frame registration can be accomplished digitally, this would obviate the need for any mechanical fine stabilization and allow the needed coadding for sensitivity improvement. There are two added benefits. First, there are gaps in the field-of-view for some on-chip filtering approaches, which could easily be filled in through this process with the aircraft forward motion and digital registration. Second, the jitter will cause subpixel shifts between the coadded frames which, after proper estimation and correction, can result in an effective microscan resolution improvement.

The on-board digital processing consists at a minimum of frame coaddition, nonuniformity correction (calibration), and data conversion to a three-color operator display. Two very important additional features, however, are envisioned. The first is an electronic stabilization process that estimates and corrects frame-to-frame motion (known or otherwise measured) in the coaddition process. This allows a sensitivity and potentially spatial resolution improvement. The second is a spectral-based automatic target cueing aid based current JMSP research in detection algorithms, including spectral matched filtering, adaptive anomaly detection, spectral unmixing, and/or model-based material identification. A digital processor sizing must still be performed.

One of the major issues yet to be addressed is the feasibility of a multi-band FLIR system that meets the stringent requirements dictated by target and background phenomenology. A hardware demonstration program is required to truly address this issue. Tables 6 to 8 provide paper designs for a number of cases, considering the radiometric and spatial performance of the central band only (the performance of the other bands will be similar). The design is based on current MCT array performance with some extrapolation to array size and frame rate.

Multi-output arrays, which can tolerate the 500 Hz frame rate, have been demonstrated, but the 1024 x 768-array size are beyond the current state-of-the-art. On the other hand, reduction to 640 x 480 would provide a commensurate reduction in field-of-view, but otherwise no system impact.

The performance estimates indicate that a Noise Equivalent Spectral Radiance, NESR, on the order of $0.1 \mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2\mu\text{msr}$ is theoretically achievable for all bands with an effective coadded frame rate of nominally 30 Hz. This supports the preservation of target color signatures and background correlation for spectral exploitation, either manual (three-color display) or automated. The 1.5 and 3 meter ground spatial distance, GSD, is likely insufficient for spatial-based detection of anything but large high contrast targets in the open, but will support spectral-based detection. In fact, a more aggressive design would relax the spatial resolution and trade it off for a larger field-of-view, consistent with calculations earlier in this memo. Even with the current FOV, an automated search could easily achieve on the order of 100-km²/min.- ground coverage.

The primary challenges of the multi-band FLIR design consist of (1) meeting the stringent requirements for sensitivity and band-to-band registration with real hardware, and (2) providing sufficient processing for the electronic stabilization and automatic target cueing. The 15 cm aperture case with 150 μrad DAS specifically results in an added difficulty in achieving the extremely high throughput (low $f/\#$) in terms of both optical design and the need for an even faster detector frame rate (1 kHz). The difficulty of this case indicates that the utility of microscanning for resolution improvement in this scenario is questionable, unless it can achieve sub-diffraction-limited resolution. Microscanning would be more useful in the 10-cm aperture case.

Detector width	20 microns		
F-number	1.33		Note: performance predictions computed only for band 2
Optics transmission	0.9		
Detector quantum efficiency	0.7		
Stray radiance	50 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2 \mu\text{msr}$		
Source temperature	300 K		
Center wavelength (band 2)	9.15 microns		
Center wavelength (band 1)	8.7 microns	Source radiance	976.9210861 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2 \mu\text{msr}$
Center wavelength (band 3)	9.35 microns	Signal transmission	0.63
		Bias transmission	0.665826845
		Etendue	1.77601E-06 cm^2sr
Frame time	2 msec		
Number of coadded frames	16		
Read noise per frame	300 electrons		
Spectral bandwidth	100 nm		
		Bias level per frame	10631991.49 electrons
		Signal level per frame	10059904.75 electrons
		Frame SNR	3072.247077
		Frame NESR	0.317982591 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2 \mu\text{msr}$
		Total SNR	12288.98831
		Total NESR	0.079495648 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2 \mu\text{msr}$
Aperture Diameter	10 cm		
Array Size (azimuth)	1024	Focal Length	13.3 cm
Array Size (elevation)	768	Frame Rate	500 Hz
Line-of Sight Range	20 km		31.25 Hz (coadded)
		IFOV	150.3759398 microradians
		GSD	3.007518797 meters
		FOV (azimuth)	8.822948666 degrees
		FOV (elevation)	6.617211499 degrees
		FOV (width)	3.079699248 km
		FOV (height)	2.309774436 km

Table 6: Multi-Band FLIR Performance Estimates
10 cm Aperture Diameter, 150 μrad DAS

Detector width	20 microns		
F-number	0.89		Note: performance predictions computed only for band 2
Optics transmission	0.9		
Detector quantum efficiency	0.7		
Stray radiance	50 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2 \mu\text{msr}$		
Source temperature	300 K		
Center wavelength (band 2)	9.15 microns		
Center wavelength (band 1)	8.7 microns	Source radiance	976.9210861 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2 \mu\text{msr}$
Center wavelength (band 3)	9.35 microns	Signal transmission	0.63
		Bias transmission	0.665826845
		Etendue	3.96616E-06 cm^2sr
Frame time	1 msec		
Number of coadded frames	32		
Read noise per frame	300 electrons		
Spectral bandwidth	100 nm		
		Bias level per frame	11871562.77 electrons
		Signal level per frame	11232777.12 electrons
		Frame SNR	3247.829183
		Frame NESR	0.300792015 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2 \mu\text{msr}$
		Total SNR	18372.49632
		Total NESR	0.053173018 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2 \mu\text{msr}$
Aperture Diameter	15 cm		
Array Size (azimuth)	1024	Focal Length	13.35 cm
Array Size (elevation)	768	Frame Rate	1000 Hz
Line-of Sight Range	20 km		31.25 Hz (coadded)
		IFOV	149.8127341 microradians
		GSD	2.996254682 meters
		FOV (azimuth)	8.789903914 degrees
		FOV (elevation)	6.592427936 degrees
		FOV (width)	3.068164794 km
		FOV (height)	2.301123596 km

Table 7: Multi-Band FLIR Performance Estimates:
15 cm Aperture Diameter, 150 μrad DAS

Detector width	20 microns		
F-number	1.78		
Optics transmission	0.9		Note: performance predictions computed only for band 2
Detector quantum efficiency	0.7		
Stray radiance	50 μ W/cm ² μ msr		
Source temperature	300 K		
Center wavelength (band 2)	9.15 microns		
Center wavelength (band 1)	8.7 microns		
Center wavelength (band 3)	9.35 microns		
		Source radiance	976.9210861 μ W/cm ² μ msr
		Signal transmission	0.63
		Bias transmission	0.665826845
		Etendue	9.91539E-07 cm ² sr
Frame time	2 msec		
Number of coadded frames	16		
Read noise per frame	300 electrons		
Spectral bandwidth	150 nm		
		Bias level per frame	8903672.079 electrons
		Signal level per frame	8424582.84 electrons
		Frame SNR	2809.182025
		Frame NESR	0.34775998 μ W/cm ² μ msr
		Total SNR	11236.7281
		Total NESR	0.086939995 μ W/cm ² μ msr
Aperture Diameter	15 cm		
Array Size (azimuth)	1024	Focal Length	26.7 cm
Array Size (elevation)	768	Frame Rate	500 Hz
Line-of Sight Range	20 km		31.25 Hz (coadded)
		IFOV	74.90636704 microradians
		GSD	1.498127341 meters
		FOV (azimuth)	4.394951957 degrees
		FOV (elevation)	3.296213968 degrees
		FOV (width)	1.534082397 km
		FOV (height)	1.150561798 km

Table 8: Multi-Band FLIR Performance Estimates:
15 cm Aperture Diameter, 75 μ rad DAS

AIR TO AIR TARGET ACQUISITION WITH AN IRST

In order to address the clutter problem most Infrared Search and Track systems (IRSTs) use something approaching the diffraction limit in angular resolution. Look down into clutter tends to require 100 - 200 μ rad DAS, similar to what we are assuming for the air to ground target acquisition, in order to suppress false alarms due to clutter. A scanning approach will be required if very large fields of regard are specified. If more moderate fields of regard are acceptable then the dual prisms discussed above may provide sufficient FOV switching to cover the necessary scan region. Besides a FOR restriction, another issue with the dual rotating prisms is the question of time response. Time response is not a problem for slewing the FOV of an A/G sensor up or down. There are no stressing timelines in that case. For an IRST the whole FOR needs to be searched once every second, or a most not less than once every 2 seconds. Whatever FOR is chosen, we need to rotate the prisms to cover this full FOR every second or two. Alternately, some novel FOV switching techniques may be considered, to simplify the mechanical system and speed up response. In addition, approaches to reduce clutter using larger DAS can be used to enlarge angular search areas (within the limit of FOV * aperture diameter discussed below). If the air to air target is handed over from an off board source then a moderate FOV will be acceptable, and a staring system can provide acceptable FOV, especially with FOV steering techniques. In table 6

we showed that a reasonable wedge prism could deflect the FOV by 30 degrees. This type of deflection would provide a 60 degree FOR for search purposes, assuming that the wedges can move the FOV fast enough to cover the necessary FOR within one or two seconds. While pilots will always want more FOR for a case in which A/G is primary, and a set of 2.5 cm diameter aperture, 1 mrad DAS, situational awareness apertures surround the aircraft, the type of FOV allowed with the steering wedges may be sufficient. If some techniques that steering brings to the table, like high rate temporal sampling, can enlarge the DAS & maintain appropriate false alarm probabilities, then we will only do better.

The pick of 8 - 10.5 μ m for spectral based search in the air to ground case is very compatible with long range IRST against somewhat low observable targets. If we assume that the plume is not available, then we are looking at a relatively low temperature greybody. Long range detection is better in the 8 - 10.5 μ m band for this case.

LASER RADAR TARGET IDENTIFICATION

The modern battlefield may consist of a mixture of friend, foe, and neutral forces. Recognition and identification of airborne and ground objects at significant ranges is therefore becoming a critical requirement for targeting systems. Electro-optical sensors, in particular laser radar, offer several distinct advantages for performing the

Figure 4: 1D, 2D, and 3D images

recognition function. These include covert interrogation because of the high directionality of the laser beam and robust recognition because of the potential for good spatial resolution at the laser wavelengths.

For the laser imaging function, we desire to make use of the same laser source used in the laser designator. This implies that the laser radar source will be solid-state, will have reasonable energy per pulse, but will be limited in pulse repetition rate to a few tens of hertz. Because of the low repetition rate, we are constrained to consider imaging modes in which the target is flood-illuminated with a laser pulse, and the image of the target is gathered on a single pulse. In addition, the energy requirements and compatibility with guidance kits also lead to the desire to operate the laser radar in the direct detection mode rather than the coherent detection mode. Direct detection does not use a local oscillator, and is a simpler system than coherent detection. Bomb guidance kits use direct detection.

In all the imaging modes the object of interest is flood-illuminated with laser energy. The reflected light is then imaged to gather information about the object. The manner in which the return energy is sampled determines the imaging mode. The imaging modes considered are one-dimensional (1-D), two-dimensional (2-D), and three-dimensional (3-D) imaging, shown in figure 4. The 1-D imaging case is much like conventional real-beam radar. In this case, all of the reflected energy is gathered by a single detector, which is sampled at a high electrical bandwidth, providing image information as a function of time. Therefore, the only geometric information obtained is along the direction of pulse propagation, i.e. in the range direction. Since this imaging mode is very similar to conventional radar, it is anticipated that radar range-only recognition algorithms may be applicable to this imaging mode.

In 2-D imaging, spatial information in azimuth and elevation, orthogonal to the direction of travel of the laser pulse, is recorded. This is often called cross-range information. There is no range information other than perhaps coarse range to the target to set a range gate about the target. The 2-D images will therefore be similar to infrared (flir) images and it is anticipated that flir recognition algorithms may be able to make use of the 2-D imagery. In fact, the flir recognition algorithms may

work better than with thermal imagery because only the geometric information will be present, which will not be dependent upon time of day and whether the target is or has been recently operating. In addition, the 2-D laser radar images will most likely be of higher resolution because of the shorter wavelength.

Three dimensional imagery will contain the most geometric information in that it will contain not only the cross-range information associated with 2-D imagery, but will also contain range to each pixel in the cross-range image. Therefore 3-D imagery will be the most robust from the point of view of target recognition. Having the 3-D position of each point in the object with respect to some origin allows the object to undergo coordinate transforms, which can simplify the recognition task and increase the ability of a human observer to identify the target. The ability to segment the object from the background is also increased. However, this imagery is the most difficult to collect on a single-pulse basis because it requires an array of high-gain detectors and an array of range counters.

The technology requirements for each of the imaging modes just described can be separated into transmitter requirements and receiver requirements. In this section we will consider the transmitter and receiver requirements associated with each of the imaging modes.

In one dimensional imaging, the laser transmitter must have large optical bandwidth such that the effective temporal width of the pulse does not blur the range image, since the range image is derived from the time history of the return signal. It is anticipated that an effective temporal pulse width of less than a few nanoseconds will be required so that a range resolution of about a foot can be achieved without significant blurring due to the pulse width. The range resolution could be achieved in a couple of ways. One way is to phase or frequency modulate the output of a long temporal pulse.⁵ The second approach is to generate laser pulses with small temporal widths directly. Either of these approaches would be satisfactory from a range resolution point of view, however other considerations dictate the use of short-time pulses. As described above, it is required that the laser operates at both an eye-safe wavelength and also at 1.06 μm . An approach to having the dual wavelengths is to begin with a 1.06 μm laser and

then convert that wavelength to one in the required eye-safe region using nonlinear optical processes. We are interested in wavelengths near 1.54 μm for reasons that will be discussed in the next paragraph.

The receiver for a 1-D imaging laser radar would consist of appropriate optics, a single detector, and readout circuitry capable of generating high range resolution imagery. To achieve a range resolution on the order of a foot requires electrical sampling of the return signal on the order of a gigahertz. The detector must be as sensitive as possible. It is preferable to operate at wavelengths above 1.5 μm where the laser is relatively eyesafe. The detector also should be compatible with gigahertz bandwidth readout. Because of the large bandwidth and the desire to operate the system at long ranges with small return signals, thermal and electrical noise will be significant. To approach shot-noise limited detection will require some form of detector gain. We have identified two approaches to the receiver technology requirements. One approach is to use InGaAs avalanche photodiodes (APD). The other approach is to insert a fiber amplifier in the receiver path; this approach requires that the transmitter wavelength be in the gain bandwidth of the fiber. For commercially available erbium-doped fiber amplifiers, this wavelength is in the 1.54 μm region. Relative advantages and disadvantages of these two approaches have been reported in the literature.⁶ The reported analysis indicated that both approaches are comparable in terms of performance

As an initial assessment of the 1-D imaging system, we have performed SNR calculations for a flood-illuminated target. Table 9 lists the parameters used in the calculation, and figure 5 shows the SNR as a function of range. We believe the parameters shown in table 9 are also consistent with an air-to-air imaging application using an APD in the receiver.

Figure 5 Signal to noise ratio for 1-D imaging as a function of range

Table 9. Parameters used in generation of Fig. 4
All distances in meters, power in Joules, time in seconds

Transmitted Beam Waist	0.0075
Transmitter Aperture	0.1
Transmitted Wavelength	1.54 10^{-6}
Transmitted Energy	400 10^{-3}
Pulse Temporal Width	1 10^{-9}
Object Range, min & max	10 10^3 to 70 10^3
Spot size at object	20
Atmospheric Extinction, db/km	-0.006
Object Cross Section	0.27
Receiver Diameter	0.15
Rcvr Effect. Focal	0.15
Trans. Loss in optics	0.5
Detector quantum efficiency	0.6
Detector diameter	85 10^{-6}
Detector electrical BW	1 10^9
Detector gain	10
Load resistance (Ohms)	500
Operating temperature (K)	300
Detector dark current (Amp)	1.5 10^{-7}

In two-dimensional imaging we no longer have a severe requirement on pulse duration. Since we are no longer gathering information in the range dimension, the pulse duration need only be short enough to allow range gating for rejection of atmospheric scattering and other forms of clutter. However, the requirement to operate at eye-safe wavelengths again drives us to pulse duration's that will be consistent with good wavelength conversion efficiency.

The receiver for the two dimensional imager has the same requirement as the 1-D imager with regards to sensitivity. However, the receiver must now have an area detector that can sample the cross-range image on a single pulse. One approach would be to use arrays of avalanche photodiodes, but such arrays at eye-safe wavelengths are not currently available. Another approach that we have identified is an image-intensified CCD (IICCD) camera.⁷ Because of the novel photocathode described in the reference, typical night vision technologies can now be applied to wavelengths in the region 1 - 1.7 μm . We have performed a theoretical assessment of this imaging mode by calculating the required illumination energy to

image an object at 20 km with one-foot cross-range resolution. Table 10 gives parameters used in calculating range for figure 6. The parameters used to generate this plot are consistent with imaging in an air-to-ground application.

Fig. 6. Illumination at faceplate of IICCD camera as a function of range for 2-D imaging

Table 10. Parameters used in Generation of Fig. 6
All distances in meters, power in Joules, time in seconds

Transmitted Beam Waist	0.0075
Transmitter Aperture	0.1;
Transmitted Wavelength	1.54 10 ⁻⁶ ;
Transmitted Energy	400 10 ⁻³ ;
Pulse Temporal Width	5 10 ⁻⁹
Object Range, min & max	10 10 ³ to 20 10 ³ ;
Spot size at object	20;
Object Reflectivity	0.3;
Receiver Diameter	0.2
Revr Effect. Focal	2.5
Trans. Loss in optics	0.5
Detector diameter	16 10 ⁻³ ;

Three-dimensional imaging on a single pulse is the most demanding from the point of view of hardware development. Requirements on the temporal pulse width

of the laser may not be as stressing as in the 1-D imaging case because range resolution may not be required, only range accuracy. The distinction between the two is that range resolution determines the ability to distinguish two scatters spaced in range, while range accuracy determines the ability to measure the range to the first scatterer within a pixel. In order to measure the range to each pixel, an array of range counters is required. A monolithic approach (single chip) to an array of range counters is being developed.⁸ This technology needs to be coupled with highly sensitive detectors (with gain) of eye-safe wavelengths. At the moment, arrays of such detectors do not exist.

LASER DESIGNATION

As stated above target designation must occur through the forward target acquisition aperture and through the situational awareness apertures. Hand off from one aperture to the other will be an important technology development. Using equation one we have the diffraction limit for a 1.06 μm designator as 51 μrad for the 2.5-cm situational awareness aperture. The large front aperture has a smaller diffraction limit, so spot size

is not a problem. Even for the situational awareness apertures the diffraction limit on the designator is small enough to provide the necessary spot size. At 20 Km a 51 μ rad angular resolution results in a spot diameter of about 1-meter. This is very accurate weapon delivery. The complete spot would be about 2 meters, with the half power points about one meter across. The difficult aspect of using this aperture for designation will be determining where to point the designator. The situational awareness passive sensor will not have more than 1024 x 1024 detector elements covering a 60 x 60 degree FOV. This is about a 1 mrad DAS. Even with microscanning, target location will not be determined to 50 μ rad accuracy. It might be determined to 300 - 500 μ rad at best. If however active tracking were used during the target identification process then precise target location could be obtained. The 1.5 μ m laser target identification system discussed above could be used to locate the target precisely and identified where we want to have the spot. The 1.06 μ m designator could also be used in a tracking / location mode at long range, where eye safety is not an issue. Some preliminary calculations show that for an ideally sensitive laser radar system we could use only 50 mj at 1.064 μ m and even assuming .1 db atmospheric attenuation, but still detect a .1 square meter target at 23 Km. If we assume a SNR of 100, 400 mj per pulse, a cross section of .1 square meters, a wavelength of 1.06 μ m, the 2.5 cm aperture diameter, and an attenuation of .1 dB per KM we calculate a range of 29.3 Km. This shows it is possible to do active tracking with a practical laser system that has more power, but also less sensitivity.

MISSILE WARNING

For Missile Warning it is assumed that we have a 1024 x 1024 element 3 -5 μ m FPA. It is possible that smaller FPAs can be used because of affordability considerations. Missile warning does not require such high resolution imaging. Other considerations (situational awareness) drive the interest in this resolution. Good missile warning performance can be obtained with a much smaller array (such as 256 x 256). Currently there is uncooled sensor performance similar to some cooled arrays in sensitivity.⁹ Uncooled detector arrays tend to be heat sensitive devices rather than quantum detectors.

The missile warning function is required to respond over a wide field of regard (up to 4 π steradians) with very short time lines (of the order of 1 second). Its performance is based on its probability of detection and false alarm rate. The sensor specification must be based not only on providing adequate sensitivity to detect the threat, but on providing suitable information to the

processor for background discrimination. In performing the discrimination, the system will often be processor limited. The sensor must be designed to provide the information required for discrimination without exceeding the capacity of the processor to analyze the data in real time. For example, a detector array with a million pixels might provide optimum sensor response, but would be useless as a warning sensor if the signal processing could not be done on the necessary time scale. One approach to a situational awareness sensor with a large format is to process some of the detector outputs in groups initially, until an area of interest has been highlighted, then to provide more detail in the area of interest. For example, a 4 x 4 detector group could initially be processed as if it were a single detector. Then once that area is highlighted the full detector resolution could be sampled.

It is expected that primary missile detection will be based on the plume band in the mid wave infrared, MWIR. This band has maximum signal for the burning missile combined with minimum background radiation. The long wave infrared, LWIR, is potentially useful for post-burnout (PBO) tracking, but PBO signatures are so low that initial detection after burnout seems unlikely.

A basic sensor concept contemplates a limited number of sensors distributed about the aircraft. A reasonable number is six. With six sensors, full 4 π coverage can be achieved with a 90° field of regard for each sensor. For most of this paper it has been assumed that the user would be willing to allow holes in coverage above & below the aircraft. This may or may not be the case. Full coverage requires each of 6 sensors to have a 90 x 90 deg coverage rather than a 60 x 60 degree coverage. A sensor could incorporate either a single detector array if a relatively large pixel is used or a cluster of arrays if very small pixels are necessary. The possibility of using room temperature thermal detectors is being explored.

A powerful discriminant against background is multicolor discrimination. This refers to the use of two or more colors to distinguish small hot burning objects from larger warm bodies that are radiating as simple black bodies. It has been shown to be a powerful discriminant for reduction of false alarms. The implementation of multicolor filtering on a staring sensor is an issue, as discussed in the air to ground target acquisition section. The required frame rate will lie somewhere in the range of 30-200 Hz. In addition to improved target tracking, the higher frame rates will facilitate obtaining adequate registration in the multicolor mode.

The performance of a warning sensor is defined by its discrimination ability as much as its sensitivity. The sensor has to be matched to the processor to ensure that the right data is available at a rate that the processor can handle. We will briefly summarize the basic generic processing algorithms of a missile warning sensor.

Detection Processing: This stage consists of filtering functions performed on the entire data set to condition the signal and maximize target-background contrast.

Gain-Offset Correction: Correct for non-uniformities in sensor response from pixel to pixel.

High Pass Filtering: Multiframe temporal filtering to remove dc pedestal from output signal.

Spatial Filtering: High pass filter to suppress extended sources. and emphasize point targets.

Spectral Differencing: Color subtraction to suppress correlated background and/or emphasize burning targets. This might be done either as a simple subtraction or weighted by an estimate of the cross correlation between bands.

Background Normalization/Thresholding: Estimate background variance to provide basis for setting thresholds for constant false alarm rate, CFAR, detection.

In warning parlance, detection means a threshold exceedance at the preprocessing level and is not to be confused with declaration. Declaration refers to the determination that a threat is actually present.

Track Processing: This stage concerns itself only with the threshold exceedances from the previous stage and is usually done in a separate computer.

Spectral False Alarm rejection: If not already performed at detection stage, this provides a quick way of rejecting detections having the wrong spectral profile without going through the track generation process.

Tracking: Correlation of detections from multiple frames to form tracks

Track assessment: Comparison of tracks with known non-threats (i.e., the sun) and assessment of tracks to determine if detection moves like a threat

Declaration: Declaration of threat and initiation of countermeasure.

The above gives some flavor of the complexity of the processing sequence which must be done on a short timeline and, to a considerable degree, limits sensor design.

IRCM VS. 3- 5 μ M SEEKERS

Air Force aircraft are becoming increasingly vulnerable to a wide range of infrared (IR) guided surface-to-air missile (SAM) and air-to-air missile (AAM) weapons. Sophisticated IR guided missiles are being developed and proliferated worldwide at an alarming rate, including imaging seekers that promise to be highly

resistive to expendable countermeasures. Many of these threats are showing up in the hands of terrorist groups as well as legitimate but potentially hostile nations.

Currently fielded infrared countermeasure (IRCM) methods rely upon expendable flares or early generation jammers. These methods are generally effective only against older, first generation IR missiles while their effectiveness against currently fielded threats as well as future advanced threats is limited. Most aircraft kills traced back to the earliest operational use of IR guided missiles have been dominated by these fire and forget weapons. The development of shoulder launched variants has allowed almost anyone to pose a serious threat to US or allied large aircraft. The IR threat has proven to be deadly on many occasions, some against USAF platforms (Gulf War). These threats are particularly serious for several reasons; first, a large number are man-portable, and thus pose a threat anywhere in the world, second, they have been exported to many third-world countries, and third, they have incorporated several effective counter-countermeasure (CCM) functions. The major United States Air Force commands (MAJCOMS) realize that currently deployed flares and early generation jammers provide limited capability and are incompatible with certain airframes and missions. The MAJCOMS desire a more effective system that is supportable and affordable.

Considerable tests and analysis has been accomplished to refine many of the IRCM requirements. Accurate missile warning is the first step to a successful IRCM engagement. The MWS must "hand-off" directional information to the IRCM system to at least one degree accuracy. This number drives the overall tracker FOR, IFOV, resolution, sensitivity, p/t stability, and a number of other factors. First the gimbal or optical system must transition to the missile coordinates. Slew rates must be on the order of 60-120 degrees per second. Typical acquisition FOR's are 6-8 degrees. Next, the system will perform a fine track on the missile. Here, the critical parameters are tracker bandwidth and overall system optical stability. Generally, we want stabilities < 300 microrad.

Finally the system will perform an interrogation of the threat, followed very closely by a countermeasure. Typically laser parameters are (depending on the a/c protected) 1-2 mRad beam divergence, 2-5 watts average power, and pulse repetition rates greater than 10khz. CW laser capability is preferred, but if not CW, the higher the rep rate, the better. We are currently considering several potential laser sources for IRCM. These include doubled co2, solid state Holmium or Yag followed by nonlinear shifts in opo's, CW Yag pumping of periodically polled

Lithium Niobate (PPLN), and semiconductor lasers. An overall assessment of the laser capabilities combined with the effectiveness against real threats will be combined for near term recommendations of lasers for existing IRCM programs. Some of these lasers lend themselves better to multifunction operation that will benefit MISSIONS, but these trade-off must be done before we can recommend a laser applicable to more than one mission.

COUNTERMEASURES AGAINST ADJUNCT TRACKERS IN THE 3-5 AND 8-12 REGION

Existing fire control systems for air-to-air and surface-to-air anti-aircraft missiles have used IR sensors, and the intelligence projections call for the increased use of these devices. These projections include the retrofit of day/night adjuncts to current threats as well as the use of these devices for new threats. While the technologies of these adjunct fire control systems is known, their use in systems is not known since there has been little activity to study them from the perspective of implementing a countermeasure

While in its early stages, it is not too early to consider how there might be synergism between the requirements for this mission and others of MISSIONS. There will likely be a strong overlap with some of the targeting requirements. Many of the detailed requirements will be similar to those stated above for IRCM, and some of the same laser technology will be applicable. If I use a 2.5 cm aperture, and I assume a 5 μm laser wavelength, then λ/D is .2 mrad. Possible IRCM parameters are: Cw or > 20 Khz rep rate laser signal with > 5 or 10 watts and a 1 mrad x 1 mrad field of view should be considered.

COVERT INTER AIRCRAFT LASER COMMUNICATIONS

Solar Blind Ultraviolet Communications would be desirable in many applications. Below are some parameters for such a system.

Transmitter

- Semiconductor Pumped Quadrupled Nd:YLF Laser
- Fiber Optic Beam Delivery System
- Wavelength: 262 nm
- Pulse repetition rate: 300 pps nominal
- Energy per pulse: 2 mJ
- Field-of-View 90 degrees
- Pulse Length: 10 ns

Receiver

- Field-of-View: 90 degrees
- Aperture size: 1.5 inch
- Photomultiplier

Communication Parameters

- Pulse Position Modulation
- 2400 BPS Voice Using LPC Vocoder
- 2400 BPS Data
- Half Duplex
- Communication Range: 1.5 km
- Construction
- Suitcase size, Battery powered

HIGH BANDWIDTH OPTICAL COMMUNICATION FOR HIGH ALTITUDE ENDURANCE UAV'S

The wavelength chosen is unimportant. It could be 1.5 μm , if that is convenient. There is a need for a very narrow filter. In the near term this means an atomic line filter. The new holographic filters will do the job, when they are available in a stable form. Currently they have 16 pm linewidths, but are somewhat unstable.^{10, 11}

The baseline requirements for our concept validation of a one gigabit optical datalink for high altitude endurance unmanned air vehicles is outlined below. The system has been sized for a 500 km range. In the system that we have baselined two light budgets which must be managed, the acquisition and tracking light budget and the communications light budget.

Acquisition/Tracking

- two 100 mw 852 nm laser
- divergence 2 mrad acquisition/500 microradian tracking
- 5.4 inch receive telescope for coarse acq/track; 1.5 inch telescope for fine tracking
- two 0.25 inch beacon transmit telescopes
- wide fov Cs atomic line filter; 0.02 nm bandpass
- CCD detector for acq/track; 7.1/6.5 pw signal required for approx 15 dB link margin

Communication

- four 200 mw 810 nm laser
- divergence 50 microrad
- 5.4 inch receive telescope for comm;
- two 1.5 inch transmit telescopes
- 5 nm interference filter
- APD detector; 60 nw signal required for 10^{-6} BER and approx 9 dB link margin

As the design evolves a number of components will be examined for the potential to reduce the terminal size and/or increase the link margins. Initially we will be looking at the use of master oscillator power amplifiers, MOPAs, for higher transmit power, better high

bandwidth detectors and lower noise charge coupled devices, CCDs.

The above is a cursory outline of the light end of the system and does not address the considerable comm high speed electronics which must be incorporated.

MULTIMODE LASER SYSTEM, INCLUDING THE FIBER NET

With the passive sensor set up as described above we will need a laser beam steerer capable of covering the 60 x 60 degrees for a 2.5 cm aperture. This beam steered can be narrowband, but it must be capable of steering laser radiation at wavelengths from 1 μm to 5 μm , and to implement countermeasures against 8 - 10 μm thermal imagers. In order to accomplish this at the required 11 speed it is that a Gires Tournios interferometer approach will be required at the longer wavelengths for beam steering.¹² Alternately newer, faster materials can be used, or possibly a micromirror approach. For any demonstration however it is preferable not to assume the invention of new materials. It is assumed the passive sensor has 360 samples per second. During each sample it is desirable that the laser beam be capable of pointing to a different location inside the passive sensor FOV. Switching speed of 1 msec or less is a reasonable requirement. The steering "mirror" must have a deflection capability of at least one wavelength, for the largest wavelength used. In this case that may be 5 μm , or up to about 10 μm .

Next I will summarize laser requirements for the active system functions. Table 11, below gives some approximate laser

parameters for the required functions. Laser Energy per pulse and power requirements certainly are approximates. In some cases I have limited energy / power based upon practical / cost considerations

I assumed that for the longer wavelength IRCM cases a degenerate optical parametric oscillator, OPO, is used to get from 1.064 to 2.13 μm . Actually doing it that way we probably can get about 30% conversion efficiency from 1.06 μm to 4 μm , but I only assumed 25%. Even using the degenerate OPO, getting to 5 μm with 25% conversion efficiency is somewhat aggressive. Quasi cw diode bars of 100 watts currently run about \$1K. Cw diodes are more expensive, and run about \$3K for 20 watts. 100 watts of cw diodes is however just \$15K, much more affordable than the 5000 watts of quasi cw diodes. There is an issue of whether all of the above applications will use the same diodes, or the cw pumped applications will be separated from the quasi cw pumped applications. At this time we should assume quasi cw diode arrays have a 5% - 20% duty cycle limitation.

Another interesting table is a wavelength table for an OPO pumped by a 1.064 μm pump. This is shown in table 12. For this table I have assumed we can convert 80% of the pump energy into one or the other new wavelengths (signal, or idler), and that the only other loss is the quantum defect. This is an aggressive assumption for pulsed conversion. Cw conversion can exceed 80%. Pulsed conversion might be more likely to be at 75%.

Table 11 Laser Parameters

Function	Wavelength	Rep Rate	Pulse Width	Ave Power	Energy / pulse	Ave power at 1.064 μm	energy per pulse 1.064 μm	Pump Energy per pulse	Pump duty cycle (200 μsec pulse)	Pump Peak power	Diode cost
IRCM (jamming)	2.5 -5.0 μm	20,000 Hz	15 nsec-200 usec	10 watts (@ 4μm)	.5 mj	40 watts	2.5 mj	10 mj	CW	200 watts	\$30K
IRCM vs FLIRs	8 - 10.5 μm										
Designator	1.06 μm, 1.54 alt	100 Hz (10 per target)	15 nsec	40 watts	400 mj	40 watts	400 mj	1.6 joule	2%	8000 watts	\$80K
ID (snaps hot)	1.5 -2.5 μm. 3.5-4 μm alt	250 Hz	3 nsec	100 watts	400 mj	194 watts	775 mj	3.1 joule	5%	15500 watts	\$160K
ID (Scanning)	1.5 -2.5 μm. 3.5-4 μm alt	20,000 Hz	3 nsec	26 watts	1.275 mj	40 watts	2.5 mj	10 mj	CW	200 watts	\$30K
Laser Comm	.266 μm	300 hz	10 - 15 nsec	.6 watts	2 mj	1.5 watts	5 mj	20 mj	6%	100	\$1K
Laser Comm	1.5 μm	125 Khz	15 nsec	25 watts	.2 mj	40 watts	.5 mj	2 mj	CW	250	39K

Table 12: OPO Wavelengths

Pump	Signal % Power	Signal	Idler
1.064 μm	55.3	1.54 μm	3.44 μm
"	54.2	1.57 μm	3.3 μm
"	40 * 2	2.12 μm	2.12 μm
"	24.3	3.5 μm	1.53 μm
"	22.7	3.75 μm	1.485 μm
"	21.3	4.0 μm	1.45 μm

For laser radar target ID wavelengths around 1.5 μm are of interest, as well as the degenerate line at 2.12, and wavelengths around 3.5 - 4 μm. The 3.5 - 4 μm region is of interest because of smoke penetration capability. A resonator structure needs to be designed to allow switching the idler and the signal, so we can chose either one as the signal of interest.

For countermeasures it seems reasonable that a degenerate OPO be used to pump a second OPO. Either that or a source around 2 μm could be used to pump the OPO. A degenerate OPO has loss, but avoids a factor of 2 of the quantum loss since two photons are generated for one photon in. This will increase the over-all efficiency. In addition, if one is interested in getting out to 5.5 μms, then more reasonable nonlinear crystal options are available. Table 13 gives estimated efficiency, and potential energy

per pulse, assuming a 250 mj per pulse pump at 1.064 μm, and 80% conversion efficiency in both OPOs. As stated earlier, that conversion efficiency is aggressive for pulsed lasers.

Table 13 Energy at mid IR. Wavelengths

Idler λ	Signal λ	Efficiency	Energy per pulse
4.8	3.8	35.7%	89
4.5	4.0	34%	85
4	4.5	30%	75
3.8	4.8	28.3%	71
3.7	5.0	27%	68
3.5	5.5	24.6%	61.5

For my assumptions this is a factor of 1.6 times more energy per pulse than if we just pumped directly with 1.064, rather than having the degenerate OPO stage. If the OPOs are less than 80% conversion efficiency, then this gain will be less. For going to the longer wavelengths it may not be possible easily in a single stage. We need a material that is transparent at 1.064 μm out to 5.5 μm. Using the degenerate OPO allows us to break this large region into two stages. There is an issue whether we have to go all the way to 5.5 μm. Laser tuneability out to 5 μm is probably sufficient against Mid IR seekers.

Another possible countermeasure mission is to counter 8 -10.5 μm thermal imagers. If an OPO is used, starting from the same 1.06 μm laser radiation, then 2 degenerate stages would be required. This would result in a pump at 4.256 μm for the final stage. Table 14 gives the power conversion efficiency if we can do 2 degenerate OPO stages, followed by an OPO.

Table 14 : LWIR Laser power from 1.06 μm

Idler wavelength	Signal wavelength	Energy efficiency
9.09 μm	8.0 μm	34 %
8.52 μm	8.5 μm	32 %
8.07 μm	9.0 μm	30 %
7.7 μm	9.5 μm	29 %
7.4 μm	10.0 μm	27 %
7.2 μm	10.5 μm	26 %

As can be seen, if we can successfully generate 2 efficient degenerate OPO stages, then reasonable energy efficient conversion can be accomplished.

Another topic of interest is the cost of designator modules, any snapshot imaging laser radar implementations, or any high energy per pulse IRCM approaches. Snapshot imaging requires high energy per pulse because the whole scene is illuminated on a single pulse and viewed with an array imager so it is possible to do identification on a single laser pulse. Diode costs for designators or snapshot imaging laser radars can be substantial. In fact it is worth considering flashlamp pumping implementations, based on cost. Diodes tend to be more reliable, and use low voltage - which is good at higher altitude.

Another interesting table is table 15, which gives estimated laser radar ranges for various conditions. These estimates are based on a crude laser radar model, but do give an idea of range for certain fixed conditions. I have assumed a signal to noise of 40, an aperture diameter of 10 cm, a minimum spot diameter of 5 meters (to flood illuminate an area), and an optics transmission of .7.

Table 15 Laser Radar Range Calculations

Wavelength	Energy	Cross section	Atten per KM	Range (Km)
1.54	400 mj	.1	.1	59 Km
2.12	400 mj	.1	.1	64.7
2.12	200 mj	.009	.1	23
1.54	500 mj	.009	.1	29.3
1.54	1.5 j	.009	.1	42
1.54	250 mj	.009	.1	22.3
2.12	500 mj	.009	.1	33.2
2.12	250 mj	.009	.1	25.5
1.56	150 mj	.009	.1	18.1
1.56	600 mj	.009	.1	31.5
1.56	60 mj	.009	.1	12.65
1.56	60 mj	.036	.1	22.1

The reason most of the cross section values are chosen as .009 is that I am interested in spatial resolution of .3 m by .3 in the cross range dimensions. At 10 % reflectivity this would be a cross section of .009 square meters, ignoring the factor of 2π associated with the two different methods of defining cross section. Larger cross section values are more appropriate when the target is not broken up into angle image space., or is broken up at lesser resolutions. The energy specified is energy per measurement. All this energy does not need to be in a single pulse. While there is some loss in efficiency with pulse integration, certainly 3 - 5 pulses could be integrated without significant integration loss. Some of the small energy per pulse numbers were my way of assuming a factor of ten attenuation through a thin cloud., but without changing the attenuation per kilometer.

The fiber net for an active system must transmit laser radiation from 1 to 5 μm , if the lasers are all kept in the systems module. The alternative is to put a laser waveform generator in the systems module, and do the power amplification and wavelength conversion at the aperture. In that case it is still assumed a single block of diode lasers would be used to pump the amplifiers. Laser diode energy would be switched from one amplifier to another through a fiber net. In that case there would be 1.06 μm waveform fiber net and a .808 μm diode pump fiber net. For high energy per pulse applications there may be a couple hundred diode bars that have to be switched, so the diode switching option requires massive switching capability for high energy per pulse applications. My preferred approach however is to generate the full laser power in the systems module. Whether or not to convert the laser energy in the systems module is another question. Nonlinear wavelength conversion generally requires a crystal and high peak powers. If wavelength conversion occurs at the aperture modules then silica fibers can be used, and they are relatively mature. Obviously this would be a stand alone system - not inside of the same cavity as an oscillator or the amplifier. If we do wavelength conversion in the systems module then we need a set of fibers that transmit from 1 to 5 μm . We should have less than 1 db loss in the fiber (assume a 10 meter fiber length, so .1 db per meter loss is acceptable). We also do not want to lose beam quality. I will assume no more than a factor of 1.2 times diffraction limited beam divergence after transmission through the fiber net. While this cannot be obtained directly in multimode fibers, there have been techniques to use phase conjugation to recover beam quality, discussed below. Another major fiber consideration is the possibility that we can have a coherent system. This means the fibers must be phase preserving. Single mode fibers are phase preserving, but result in low peak power handling capability.

We discuss an approach to transmitting high power through fibers without having poor transmitted beam

quality. This approach has

Figure 7. Phase Congugate Mirror use in near diffraction limited transmission of High Power through Fiber Systems

been developed by Hughes research labs.¹³ The laser is located remotely from the aperture. They are connected by a pair of fibers. The approach is based on a master oscillator power amplifier (MOPA) concept incorporating a phase conjugate mirror (PCM). This is shown schematically in Figure 7, where the beam shapes shown in the square boxes and large speckled beam are experimentally measured at the input and output of the fibers. Hughes did its experimental work with Nd:YAG to demonstrate the viability of this approach, but this architecture is readily applicable to other laser systems or wavelengths also.

The oscillator produces excellent output beam at low enough power that it can be transmitted to the aperture (output coupler) via a single mode reference fiber, which maintains the lowest order spatial profile. This beam is injected into the beam delivery fiber, which has a large enough core (can be a fiber bundle also) to carry the desired output power. The beam traveling in the beam delivery fiber toward the laser amplifiers gets highly distorted. This distorted beam passes through the amplifiers, gets amplified somewhat, and enters the phase conjugate mirror (PCM). The PCM reflects this beam with the correct phase front to compensate for the distortions generated in the fiber as well as the amplifiers. This reflected beam extracts the energy in the amplifier during its second pass and gets amplified, traverses the fiber again, and emerges at the output coupler with full energy and very with beam quality as good as the input from the oscillator.

This approach requires that the laser and the fiber delivery system be thought out and designed together. One may argue it adds some complexity, but it is the only way to obtain very good beam quality with laser beam delivered to the aperture by a multimode fiber, which can be required for delivery of high power laser signals.

In some special circumstances it is possible to use a multimode fiber and still maintain reasonably good beam quality at the exit of the fiber. These are very special and have to be looked at on an individual basis.

Given the various fiber discussions above MISSIONs may need 3 or 4 fiber nets for a complete system. One net will carry high peak power laser transmissions at 1.06 μm through 1.6 μm . This net could use the phase conjugate architecture to obtain good beam quality. A second net could cover IR jamming. If wavelength conversion is in the systems module then the IR countermeasures net will use chalcogenite fibers with $< .1$ db per meter loss. Another net could be single mode phase preserving fibers, covering from 1.5 to 2.1 μm for coherent laser radar. We might even want the single mode fibers to cover 1.5 to 4.2 μm , so the coherent laser radar function can tune over these wavelengths. It is also possible that the high peak power fiber net would usefully carry signals out to 4.2 μm if any damage countermeasure approaches are considered. For both of these nets however, near term cut off at shorter wavelengths is acceptable. Lastly there will of course be a high bandwidth digital net. There could be a fifth net for passive sensors if optical matched filter pattern recognitions is used for target detection or if images can be transmitted efficiently. It may be possible to put needed image information into a single mode fiber, and therefore such an additional net could be used either at the detected passive wavelength, or at some converted wavelength. If wavelength conversion is done at the aperture modules then the only fiber nets one needs are for 1.06 μm . The single mode / phase preserving net or the multimode net might be able to do IRCM. Figure 8 shows a possible fiber architecture.

Figure 8. Possible Fiber Net / Multimode laser system

LOW COST PER FUNCTION OPEN ARCHITECTURE RF SENSORS

The purpose of this section is to consider an open architecture, low cost per function, RF sensor system. It is envisioned that an RF system will include all communications, targeting, and electronic warfare functions. It is envisioned that the system will be designed for lowest cost per function, including cost of maintenance and technical currency. Total systems cost will be low, but the system will be capable of a large number of user defined functions. Some functions will be federated and some will be integrated, depending on engineering judgment as to how

we best achieve both low initial cost and low cost for a system lifetime that includes many changes due both to technology change and requirements change. These two forces for change will drive much of lifetime systems cost for a system that is kept current in performance. Because of the need for continued change over the long lifetime of a system it is very important to have open architecture in the sense that the system can practically be updated at an affordable cost. We have learned that being open in this sense is more difficult than being open architecture in a formal systems sense. Figure 9 shows the functions such an RF sensor system could perform.

Figure 9. RF Sensor System Functions

The generic architecture shown in figure 10 is the best near to moderate term architecture for an RF system that must be low cost but perform many diverse functions. Communications is mostly a low band system. It is also becoming very

Figure 10: Generic Multifunction RF Systems Architecture

inexpensive, so it should be a separate system, except for some common elements such as the backplane. EW has a unique problem of needing a wideband receiver. It should be separate. Radar needs high dynamic range and can use narrow band, so it is a separate receiver. This receiver may also be used for other functions such as precision location for electronic warfare. The generic architecture shown in figure 10 is very compatible with excellent use of A/D converter technology. It is desirable if all modules can plug into a common backplane, use common voltages, and where possible use common physical interfaces. Substantial hardware can be saved by digitizing near the aperture. In order to share resources across these threads within current A/D state of the art, processing would have to remain in the analog domain for a longer period of time, thus requiring more resources. Fiber optic switching technology will substantially reduce the weight of the switches but as of this time will not do much for the cost.

We recommend added focus on the engineering ramifications of moving the A/D converter closer to the antenna. For example, will faster digital signal processors be required? Will faster, wide band digital data busses be required? The system design must facilitate acceptance of product improvements such as added receiver channels and technology advancements with a minimum of engineering. There are also environmental considerations. The aperture can be placed in a hostile environment. Required environmental conditions and impacts need to be considered. Another area that needs to be looked at is the architecture / device state of the art for signal generation. Direct Digital Synthesis (DDS) could save significant cost when these devices become available. Some signal distribution may be appropriate based upon the cost of individual signal generators and the cost of signal distribution. The state of the art in fiber technology will influence the cost of signal distribution while DDS technology will influence the cost of signal generation.

It does not make sense to integrate certain sensors such as Global Positioning System and radar altimeters because they are so inexpensive on the commercial market. The rest of the radio frequency avionics can be broken up into the three categories already discussed, Communication- Navigation- Identification (CNI), radar, and electronic warfare (EW). RF requirements for the equipment in each of these three categories are different. CNI equipment tends to require narrow bandwidths and carrier frequencies below two gigahertz. Radar requires a high frequency carrier (above eight thousand megahertz), narrow bandwidth, and wide dynamic range. Electronic warfare systems tend to require high frequencies, wide bandwidths, and relatively low dynamic range. While all three categories of equipment use the same basic building blocks, i.e. oscillators, amplifiers, mixers, filters, and switches, these building blocks have significantly different performance requirements for the different equipment. Some common building blocks may be used between the threads, but there will also be unique hardware. Given the definition of the 3 threads that will be used the exact module building blocks need to be defined.

Software validation & verification issues can be substantial for an integrated system. To check out all the potential modes in a multifunction system is very expensive. This is an issue we have to address or no multifunction system will be cost effective. This issue is a critical issue even if the 3 threads of radar, communications, and EW are kept separate. We need the ability to isolate different parts of the system and prove that they are isolated so we will not have to test any functions outside of that particular isolated "module". You will only have to test modes contained in the isolated region. The difficult part of that scenario is really proving isolation, especially for a new set of algorithms. Even widely distributed commercial software programs sometimes need patches to work with other widely distributed programs. **If we do not accomplish isolation, then we will have to conduct many expensive tests to do any modification to an integrated system.** That will drive the cost of modifying integrated systems into a much higher bracket than federated systems. **In effect rather than being open the complex multifunction integrated system will become impractical to change.** Firewall research used for the internet may be applicable. There is a basic research issue of the complexity associated with modifying complex integrated systems. Until we can prove firewall installation between modes we will have to keep processing separate in order to afford system upgrades. We cannot afford to use a single central processor until a proven isolated modules strategy is developed.

The idea of standardizing backplane voltage to the extent possible is a profitable approach to open up the architecture and is to be commended independent of whether federated or integrated modules are used. Another similar area that is to be commended is the effort to show isolation between modules of different types. This provides more flexibility in module placement whether the modules are federated or integrated. The definition of a common RF rack, back plane, and interconnects (open system architecture) could help reduce the cost of ownership by allowing redesign to occur on a module by module basis instead of requiring redesign of an entire RF subsystem.

Another issue is one of fault tolerance. If the reliability of modules increases this becomes a less pressing issue, but it will always be a wartime damage issue, even if modules that last the life of the aircraft are developed. Common resource modules are applicable to fault tolerant designs. Federated approaches are more difficult to re-prioritize during flight so we can adjust to battle damage or parts failure. Many modules are currently projecting very long lifetimes, so battle damage becomes the major reason for fault tolerant designs. One of the major issues for fault tolerant design is now becoming connectors and interconnects. From an architecture point of view as well as component development we have probably not put enough emphasis in this area. Reducing the number of connectors / interconnects and developing avionics equipment design strategies for preventing failures over a long aircraft lifetime should be a major area of emphasis.

Future systems may have receivers (A/D interface) moved forward within the manifold at the subarray level & not just as a single output of the entire array. This will allow expanded beam forming flexibility & reconfigurable aperture element/subarray utilization for simultaneous beam formation. This type of trend, will not be as amenable to integrated time shared receivers, but we need to consider it because of the long life planned for future systems. Adding multiple channels should be a planned growth path for the narrow bandwidth (nominal radar) thread.

Another area that needs additional consideration is the area of multiple ship operation. An electronically scanned array can be used both for jamming and radar, but not at the same time. It is possible that in a multiple ship formation one ship can be using its radar to deliver ordinance while the other ships are doing support jamming. In a single ship activity the concept of using the forward array both for jamming and radar use does

not make sense because you need heavy jamming at the time you are delivering ordinance. We do endorse the idea of using a nose, scanned, array for jamming in a multiple ship formation context, for jamming that is a spin off capability to the radar development. Major cost should not be incurred to add this capability, but we should investigate trying to accomplish this multiple ship formation capability.

Next we will discuss general approaches to reducing the cost of an RF system that accomplishes many functions. In order to attempt to quantify the cost impacts on federated, completely integrated, or a system architecture somewhere in between cost needs to be broken into three areas. A breakdown is recommended because all approaches / items do not effect the 3 cost categories the same. The categories are:

- 1) Acquisition cost
- 2) Life cycle cost
- 3) Retro-fit cost

In order to evaluate approaches to cost reduction in these categories we need to define/agree on what affects cost in the three areas. The following is an initial start.

What affects acquisition cost?

- a) High product development (NRE) cost for many different types of hardware units
- b) Expensive small volume unit fabrication costs
- c) Expensive software development cost

How can Acquisition cost be reduced?

- a) Reduce NRE design time/cost
- b) Incorporate flexible manufacturing for low cost low volume fabrication costs
- c) Reduce the number of "types" of hardware needed to be developed
- d) Increase manufacturing volume via commonality
- e) Insert new adequately mature technology
- f) Utilize "Commercial hardware/practices" where applicable.
- g) Reduce software development costs

What affects Life Cycle Cost?

- a) Extensive flight line maintenance
- b) Inadequate BIT/fault isolation
- c) Large inventory of spare parts
- d) Unavailable outdated technology/components

How can life cycle cost be reduced?

- a) Only have scheduled maintenance, except for war damage, and only have maintenance at the depot rather than in the field and at multiple locations.

- b)Employ adequate BIT to all levels of system
- c)Develop functional behavioral description of system to allow technology independent hardware replacements (addressed by past VHDL, MHDL & other work on hardware descriptive languages/behavioral modeling programs)
- d)Maintain technology current design hardware updates (concept of design model year as applied to automotive industry)

What affects Retro-Fit Costs?

- a)Software updates
- b)Major airframe modifications
- c)Large inventory of spare parts
- d)System architecture
- e.)Testing costs after changes are made

How can Retro-Fit costs be reduced?

- a) Employ hardware independent operating systems
- b) Utilize software encapsulation/functional isolation
- c)Low profile/conformal apertures
- d)Highly integrated components
- e)Hardware behavioral descriptive capability for replacement/enhancement

Next we will talk briefly about a business perspective on how we partition the modules in an RF system. Terry Tucker from ENA provided Figure 10. The figure illustrates that in one model we pay a much higher pass through cost than in the other model.

Figure 10: Overhead Pass Through Cost for each Architecture

The other chart from Terry Tucker is Figure 11. He maintains that the ability to move away from flight test into less expensive forms of testing, as shown in the lower left corner of the chart, is dependent on using a more federated architecture because each module contractor can test his own equipment. In a highly

integrated approach a box doesn't do any useful function by itself, so it is difficult to test a module until a full system is assembled.

The last business issue comment has to do with the profit motive. For contractors to invest in developing the "modules" we need, they must see a profit. If we can define modules that will be used across a wide variety of platforms then contractors will invest. If we define unique modules we will pay the full bill for all of our modules because there will not be a large market to drive contractor investment. In saying we "define modules" what is meant in

Figure 11. Reducing Higher Order Testing for Integrated vs Federated Approaches.

this context is that we define certain input and output interfaces, both with respect to information content and physical interfaces. The contractor is free to put anything he wishes between the interfaces, so long as the correct information comes out, given the correct input. In this way the contractor is free to control the content of the modules, and can insert new technology as it becomes available. What must be defined is the appropriate interfaces, and ideally the same set of interfaces can be applied to multiple applications in order to increase volume on a given module type.

CONCLUSIONS

- 1.) Design of a complete multifunction EO sensor systems at the same time should allow significant cost savings.
- 2.) Development of multifunction laser systems are required.
- 3.) Development of a fiber distribution system for laser energy is required.
- 4.) Software that is independent of hardware implementation will be required for affordable sensor lifetimes. This may imply a new compiler being

delivered with new hardware so there will be no required change in software.

- 5.) The use of common modules is required to lower costs. In this context "common modules" mean using the same interface specifications in more than one application. The contractor would be free to change the content of the modules, so long as the information and physical interfaces remain the same.
- 6.) A/D technology availability will drive affordable R/F systems architecture approaches.
- 7.) Any multifunction system developed must have functional isolation firewalls that will limit the amount of testing required in order to make system changes.
- 8.) Consideration needs to be given to module commonality across platforms.
- 9.) On the business level DOD needs to have a fund that rewards system program offices for developing approaches that benefit all of DOD.
- 10.) Common backplane and common voltage architecture should be developed, as well as common modules. Backplane architecture must support growth.
- 11.) IEEE type (i.e. commercially supported) standards should be pursued for interfaces.
- 12.) More attention needs to be paid to cables and interconnects. They account for a significant number of the failures of electronic systems.
- 13.) We need to look at accelerated development of direct digital synthesis for radar and EW application as a method of lowering cost of these functions.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to acknowledge a number of people who contributed to the development of the thoughts expressed for both the EO and RF sections. For the EO section people besides the co-authors who contributed include: Duanne Smith, Al Jelalian, Metin Manger, Jon Mooney, Terry Dorschner, Ish Aggerwal, Ken Barnard, and Pat Gardner. For the RF section I would like to acknowledge John Hines, Steve Kiss, Emil Martinsek, John Lee, and Terry Tucker. Mike Borky had influence on the whole paper based on suggestions and discussions.

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